

dormancy is 10-15 d at harvest. It yields 5.5 to 6.0 t/ha.

WGL 22245 (IR579/W12708) is 80 cm tall with compact panicles. Leaves have a purple margin. It is photoperiod-insensitive with 125-d duration in monsoon and 135 d in winter. Grains are translucent. It has stem borer (SB) and

bacterial blight resistance, and yields 6.0 to 7.5 t/ha. It is recommended for release as Pothana.

WGL 26889 (IR22/12708) is a 145-d variety suitable for the monsoon season. It is SB-resistant with fine grains, and yields an average 6.0 t/ha. It is being tested in minikit trials.

WGL 20506 (Tella Hamsa/W12708) has 105-d duration and is especially suited for sowing in late monsoon, as late as mid-Aug. Grains are long and slender with a light brown husk. Yield averages 4.5 to 5.0 t/ha. □

Reaction of yellow stem borer (YSB) resistant accessions to other rice pests

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In the greenhouse we tested six accessions with resistance and moderate resistance to YSB for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH), whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), green leafhopper (GLH), leafhopper (LF), white leafhopper (WLH), and rice tungro virus (RTV).

W1263 was resistant to LF, BPH, WBPH, and GLH and moderately resistant to RTV (see table). Co 18 and

Reaction of YSB resistant accessions to major rice pests and RTV, Coimbatore, India.

Accession	Mean resistance rating ^a						
	YSB	GLH	WLH	BPH	WBPH	LF	RTV ^b
W1263	1.0 a	4.0 a	6.3 bc	3.6 a	4.3 a	1.8 a	5.0 a
Co 18	4.0 bc	6.0 ab	3.6 a	3.6 a	3.6 a	6.2 bc	7.6 c
IR13641-4	4.0 bc	7.0 bc	6.3 bc	7.6 cd	5.0 ab	6.6 c	7.0 bc
IR13639-39	4.0 bc	5.6 ab	5.6 b	5.6 b	5.0 ab	5.4 b	5.0 a
Sornavazhai	6.5 c	7.0 bc	7.6 cd	3.0 a	4.3 a	9.0 d	7.0 bc
Jaya (susceptible)	9.0 d	6.5 abc	5.0 ab	7.0 bc	6.3 ab	9.0 d	9.0 d
TN1	—	9.0 c	9.0 d	9.0 d	7.6 b	—	—

^aBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not statistically different. ^bRating scale based on field evaluation.

IR13639-39 were moderately resistant to BPH, WBPH, and WLH. IR13641-4 was moderately resistant to WBPH and

moderately susceptible to other pests. Sornavazhai was resistant to BPH and WBPH. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Tolerance for iron deficiency in rice

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Fe deficiency is a major constraint to increasing the area planted to high yielding varieties in the calcareous soils of north Bihar. Major calcareous areas are in Gopalganj, Saran, Siwan, Vaishali, Muzaffarpur, Samastipur, Begusarai, East Champaran, and parts of West Champaran and Darbhanga.

Soils have pH 7.7 to 9.8, electrical conductivity 0.1 to 4.2 dS/m, 0.1 to 1.0% organic carbon, 4 to 49% available CaCO₃, and low available P. Nurseries are dry-seeded and seedling leaves whiten in the nursery beds. Fe deficiency

symptoms are yellowing of young leaves and interveinal chlorosis which becomes whitish yellow, then ivory.

Varieties differ in susceptibility to Fe deficiency. We screened lines for Fe deficiency in the field at Pusa beginning in 1981 wet season. The first trial was non-replicated. In the next, tolerant lines were evaluated in three replications. Symptoms

were visible 15 to 20 d after seeding. IET7972 and IET7973 were tolerant of Fe deficiency. Br 34, Br 8, and TCA84 were moderately tolerant (Table 1). Most of the released varieties were susceptible to highly susceptible. Tolerant and moderately tolerant entries were photoperiod sensitive and are pureline selections from land races.

Table 1. Varietal reaction of certain elite lines to Fe deficiency, Samastipur, India.

Tolerance score	Plant infection (%)	Line
1	up to 1	IET7972 (TCA148-3), IET7973 (TCA62-31-1)
3	1 – 5	Br34, Br8, TCA84
5	5 – 25	UPR238-42-2-3, IET5882, UPR79-17, T141, NP49, IET6263
7	25 – 50	Rasi (IET1444, Pankaj, Janaki (IET9971), IET7970, KMP40, IET5883
9	50 – 100	Pusa 33, Pusa 2-21, Ratna, Rajendra Dhan 201, Sita, Jaya, Mahsuri, Saket 4, Radha (IET6261), UPR79-14, IR4568-86-1-2-3, RP1045-403-1, IR1157-52, UPR254-81-1-TCA, Br9, Katarni